

Questionnaire Items for Octalysis Core Drives in Requirement Change Management

Supplementary material

The questionnaire was designed to measure practitioners' perceptions of the Octalysis Core Drives within the context of Requirement Change Management (RCM). Each item was constructed to capture a specific indicator of motivation, such as role significance, meaningful belonging, work importance, and contribution.

Responses were collected using a four-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The decision to use a four-point scale was deliberate, as it avoids the neutral midpoint and indirectly encourages respondents to take a clearer stance on each statement. This approach enhances the ability of the data to reflect the actual tendencies of respondents' attitudes, thereby producing results that are more interpretable and actionable.

The questionnaire was administered to RCM practitioners actively engaged in software development projects, ensuring that responses were grounded in real-world professional contexts. Each item was carefully reviewed for content validity and alignment with the underlying theoretical constructs of the Octalysis Framework. Furthermore, prior to full deployment, the questionnaire underwent pilot testing to ensure clarity, comprehensibility, and face validity among the target respondents.

In addition, reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha confirmed internal consistency for each set of items corresponding to the eight core drives, with all values exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.70. Construct validity was also supported by item-total correlation tests, which demonstrated significant associations between each item and its respective construct. Taken together, these steps provide confidence that the instrument is both valid and reliable for measuring motivational constructs in the gamified RCM context.

No	Code	Core Drive	Indicator	Question Statement
1	EMC1	Epic Meaning & Calling	Role significance	I feel that my role in every project I participate in is meaningful.
2	EMC2	Epic Meaning & Calling	Meaningful belonging	Gamification in Jira makes me feel like I am part of something meaningful.
3	EMC3	Epic Meaning & Calling	Work importance	I am motivated to work harder because I believe my work is important to the projects I am working on.
4	EMC4	Epic Meaning & Calling	Contribution impact	I feel that my contributions have a significant impact on the outcome of the project.

5	DAP1	Development & Accomplishment	Progress visibility	Gamification in Jira helps me see my progress and achievements at work.
6	DAP2	Development & Accomplishment	Reward satisfaction	I feel satisfied when I reach a level or earn points in gamification.
7	DAP3	Development & Accomplishment	Quality motivation	I feel motivated to complete tasks with high quality because of the rewards.
8	DAP4	Development & Accomplishment	Level striving	I am motivated to continue improving my level or achievements in Jira.
9	DAP5	Development & Accomplishment	Work productivity	I feel more productive in my work because of the achievement system in Jira.
10	DAP6	Development & Accomplishment	Achievement feeling	Gamification in Jira gives me a real sense of achievement in my work.
11	ECF1	Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback	Creative expression	Gamification in Jira allows me to express my creativity in completing tasks.
12	ECF2	Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback	Creative thinking	I feel encouraged to think creatively in achieving project goals through gamification.
13	ECF3	Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback	Idea recognition	Gamification helps me see that my ideas are valued within the team.
14	ECF4	Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback	New approach	I feel more motivated to try new approaches in my work because of gamification.
15	ECF5	Empowerment of Creativity & Feedback	Creativity appreciation	I often receive appreciation for my creativity and initiative in tasks in Jira.
16	OWP1	Ownership & Possession	Role ownership	I feel that I play an important role in the achievements and progress of this project through gamification.
17	OWP2	Ownership & Possession	Reward pride	The rewards and achievements I have earned in Jira make me feel proud.
18	OWP3	Ownership & Possession	Task responsibility	I feel responsible for the results of the tasks I complete in Jira.
19	OWP4	Ownership & Possession	Work attachment	I feel more connected to my work because of the gamification in Jira.
20	SIR1	Social Influence & Relatedness	Team connection	Gamification makes me feel more connected to my teammates.

21	SIR2	Social Influence & Relatedness	Collaboration drive	I feel more motivated to collaborate with the team because of gamification.
22	SIR3	Social Influence & Relatedness	Peer feedback	I often give and receive appreciation from my teammates in gamification on Jira.
23	SIR4	Social Influence & Relatedness	Peer recognition	Gamification helps me feel valued by my colleagues.
24	SIR5	Social Influence & Relatedness	Active participation	I feel encouraged to actively participate in the team because of the social elements in gamification.
25	SIR6	Social Influence & Relatedness	Supportive environment	I feel that gamification makes the work environment more supportive and collaborative.
26	SIM1	Scarcity & Impatience	Urgent reward	I feel compelled to complete tasks quickly in order to earn limited rewards.
27	SIM2	Scarcity & Impatience	Limited chance	Gamification in Jira makes me want to complete challenges quickly before the opportunity disappears.
28	SIM3	Scarcity & Impatience	Rare reward	I feel more motivated to complete tasks because of the rare rewards.
29	SIM4	Scarcity & Impatience	Fast working	I feel that the limited rewards in gamification motivate me to work faster.
30	UPC1	Unpredictability & Curiosity	Surprise interest	I am interested in continuing to participate in gamification because of the element of surprise.
31	UPC2	Unpredictability & Curiosity	Reward curiosity	I am curious about the new challenges or rewards that may arise in gamification.
32	UPC3	Unpredictability & Curiosity	Uncertainty drive	The element of uncertainty in gamification makes me want to know more.
33	UPC4	Unpredictability & Curiosity	Fun surprise	I feel that the element of surprise makes gamification in Jira more interesting and enjoyable.
34	UPC5	Unpredictability & Curiosity	Future curiosity	I feel motivated to continue participating because I don't know for sure what will happen next in gamification.
35	LOA1	Loss & Avoidance	Loss prevention	I am motivated to stay active so that I don't lose my achievements in gamification.

36	LOA2	Loss & Avoidance	Work discipline	I feel that the element of loss aversion in gamification makes me more disciplined in my work.
37	LOA3	Loss & Avoidance	Reward protection	I feel motivated to avoid losing points or rewards in gamification.
38	LOA4	Loss & Avoidance	Reputation keeping	Gamification in Jira encourages me to complete tasks to maintain my reputation or achievements.